

Accelerating the Construction of Complex Geometries in OpenMC with ELSA

Paul A. Ferney ^{1,*}

¹Idaho National Laboratory, 1955 Fremont Ave, Idaho Falls, ID

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803968

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the Engineering Layer for System Analysis (ELSA), a Python code layer built on top of OpenMC, designed to assist users in efficiently creating and modifying complex OpenMC models. ELSA offers several innovations to streamline model creation: (i) a node-based geometry generation paradigm inspired by ROOT and Geant4, (ii) on-the-fly creation of multiple regions to reduce redundancy in the code, (iii) generation of parametric regions from 2D sketches similar to CAD software, and (iv) advanced universe manipulation for dynamic configuration model generation workflows. These tools have been successfully applied to the study of the TREAT reactor, significantly enhancing the process of geometry creation and model generation.

Keywords: ELSA, OpenMC, Geometry generation

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Idaho National Laboratory (INL) has witnessed significant advancements in various ambitious nuclear projects. The Transient Reactor Test Facility (TREAT) was successfully restarted in 2017 [1], and numerous experiments have since been conducted [2, 3, 4]. The Demonstration of Microreactor Experiments (DOME) was designed to facilitate comprehensive testing of diverse microreactor designs [5]. Additionally, the System Physics Advanced Reactor Critical Facility (SPARC) was conceptualized at INL [6] to establish new critical benchmarks in line with contemporary advancements in reactor designs and technologies.

These projects heavily rely on simulation tools, particularly Monte Carlo codes, for neutron and photon transport computations. Unlike the standardized code chains used in commercial reactor exploitation, which prioritize efficiency and performance, the codes employed for designing and analyzing experiments in test reactors must be robust and versatile.

Traditional Monte Carlo codes such as MCNP [7], SCALE-KENO [8], Serpent2 [9], and TRIPOLI4 [10] have proven capabilities and have been reliable tools for experiment analysis and design. However, these approaches depend on keyword-based input datasets, and obtaining the source code for independent development can be challenging. In the past decade, an alternative has emerged: OpenMC [11]. It is an open-source Monte Carlo code with a Python API to create input datasets. These features allow for faster development of reactor models and the creation of custom tools for specific reactor physics problems [12, 13].

Nevertheless, this already powerful Python API can still be enhanced. In scenarios where many different models must be created to simulate changing experiments, as in TREAT, DOME, or SPARC, repetitive actions are often required. Specifically, the user must create surfaces, combine them into regions, and fill them with different compositions. This process can lead to errors if regions are not correctly constructed or if certain spatial regions are overlooked. Consequently, geometry creation becomes both slow and error-prone, necessitating time to identify and rectify issues. To address these challenges, the option exists to use CAD models in OpenMC using the available DAGMC capabilities [14]. However,

*paul.ferney@inl.gov

this approach sacrifices direct control over geometry definition to rely on external files. An interesting approach is used by ROOT [15] and Geant4 [16] codes. Unlike traditional approaches, which rely on surface-based primitives and require explicit cell definitions to fill all regions of space, the node-based approach generates primitive regions that are combined using Boolean operations, rotations, and translations. A tree structure is then employed to efficiently manage space filling, with certain regions being filled implicitly. This paradigm has proven relevant for Monte Carlo codes, as it is possible to use ROOT geometry files with TRIPOLI4. It reduces the time needed to generate a model and the possibility of errors in region definition and space filling.

The Engineering Layer for System Analysis (ELSA) is a Python layer built on top of OpenMC that implements this paradigm alongside new capabilities, such as extrusion and revolution of 2D sketches and advanced universe manipulation functions to enhance model creation efficiency. The development of ELSA was primarily driven by the need for a tool to quickly create and modify experiment designs in the TREAT reactor. However, ELSA can be extended to various other experiment design and analysis cases.

This paper presents three new tools to expedite the creation of OpenMC geometries. Section 2 describes a node-based geometry approach similar to Geant4. Section 3 presents tools to generate regions parametrically. Section 4 introduces advanced ways to manipulate universes.

2. NODE-BASED GEOMETRIES

This section compares the implementation of node-based geometry in both ROOT and ELSA.

2.1. Node-Based Geometry in ROOT

The node-based geometry approach in ROOT consists of the following steps:

1. Defining regions of space using boolean operations on primitives.
2. Defining each node with a region and a material composition.
3. Defining the hierarchy between nodes in a tree structure (see Figure 1). If a node is added to another node, it overrides the composition of the previous node in the region of the new node.

Figure 1. ROOT Geometry Tree.

The concept of a node may appear similar to the concept of a cell in OpenMC. However, the region of a cell must be explicitly defined by the user, which can easily cause errors if the user does not manage region overlaps or empty space correctly. In contrast, the node region is determined implicitly based on the node tree structure, partially eliminating room for error. Implicit region definition is also present in other Monte Carlo codes, though implemented differently, such as “holes” in KENO, “background volumes” in Serpent2, and “layered geometry” in Shift.

2.2. Node-Based Geometry in ELSA

A limitation of the node-based geometry paradigm of ROOT is that it does not rely on the concept of a universe. A universe is a collection of cells that the user can use to fill a given region. Some geometries can be more easily defined by creating different universes. For example, if a bottle is filled with water to a certain height, it is easier to define a universe filled with water up to that height and then fill the inner region of the bottle than to determine the actual region occupied by the water (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Bottle geometry with ROOT and ELSA.

Additionally, the tree structure is not always ideal as nodes must be added one by one. It would be more straightforward for users to add multiple nodes to a single master node or to add a full chain of nodes at once.

This is why ELSA introduces the concept of a submodel. A submodel is a class that takes a list of regions and fills (which can be material compositions, universes, lattices, or other submodels) and creates a dedicated universe based on a set of rules. The types of submodels available in ELSA are:

- **Homogeneous:** A homogeneous submodel is a quick and easy way to create a universe filled with a certain composition, which can be later used, for example, in a lattice or as a dummy universe while building a complex geometry.
- **Onion:** An onion submodel consists of a collection of nodes added successively, like the concentric shells of an onion (see Figure 3). This submodel is particularly relevant for geometries like TRISO fuels.
- **Peas:** A peas submodel consists of a collection of non-overlapping nodes added to a master node, like peas in their shell (see Figure 4). This submodel is particularly relevant for holes in a vessel part or pellets in a fuel rod.

ELSA automatically generates surfaces, half-spaces, regions, explicit cells, and universes with OpenMC for each submodel.

Figure 3. Onion Submodel.

Figure 4. Peas Submodel.

3. PARAMETRIC GENERATION

This section dives into the differences between ELSA and native OpenMC capabilities for region generation.

3.1. Region Generation in OpenMC and ELSA

OpenMC has low-level functions to create regions: the user must first create surfaces that divide space into two half-spaces (e.g., planes, spheres, cylinders, cones, quadrics), then combine these half-spaces into regions using boolean operations. However, this process can result in errors for beginner users when the region definitions are too complex, making the resulting geometries difficult to debug.

OpenMC has capabilities to generate specific regions more easily using composite surfaces. It is possible to generate boxes, one-sided cones, right circular cylinders, etc. OpenMC also has functions to generate TRISO particles.

Despite these advantages, users still need to contend with the concept of surfaces and half-spaces. In contrast, ELSA aims to simplify the user experience by focusing solely on regions. Accordingly, most OpenMC composite surface functions are rewritten to generate primitive regions. Additionally, as many primitive regions have similar input parameters (e.g., holes of the same dimensions in a vessel), ELSA leverages functions to easily create multiple regions with the same parameters, minimizing the risk of error. For example:

```
holes = elsa.MultiRegionGenerator.ZRods(
    x0=[1.,0.,-1.,0.],
    y0=[0.,1.,0.,-1.],
    r=0.25,
    z0=-1.,
    z1=+1.
)
```

creates a list of regions corresponding to four right circular cylinders with a radius of 0.25 cm and a height of 2 cm.

The same logic allows the user to create a list of regions based on a list of transformations:

```
hole = elsa.RegionGenerator.ZRod(x0=1.,y0=0.,r=0.25,z0=-1.,z1=+1.)
holes = elsa.MultiTransformGenerator.AxisRotates(
    region=hole,
    angle_in_deg=[0., 90., 180., 270.],
    axis_origin=(0.,0.,0.),
    axis_vector=(0.,0.,1.),
)
```

which creates the same list of regions.

3.2. Sketches and Parametric Capabilities

ELSA also significantly streamlines the creation of complex regions, resembling CAD software. Indeed, ELSA has a sketch tool and a parametric generation tool that allow for the creation of both extruded and revolved regions. The process to generate a parametric region is presented in Figure 5 and is as follows:

- Create a set of 2-dimensional points that form a polygon. The polygon does not have to be convex. In the case of an extruded sketch along the Z-axis, the 2D coordinates represent the (x, y) coordinates. In the case of a revolved sketch around the Z-axis, the 2D coordinates represent the (r, z) coordinates. The r coordinates must be positive. The first and last r coordinates must be equal to zero.
- Transform some segments into circular curves by selecting two consecutive points and giving curve parameters (e.g., radius, tangency, third point).
- Provide the created sketch to a parametric function, which takes a sketch as input and outputs an extruded or revolved region.

As a result, it is possible to generate very complex models quickly. For example, the simplified PWR geometry presented in Figure 6 required less than 400 lines of Python code.

Figure 5. Geometry of the TWIST experiment in TREAT.

Figure 6. Simplified PWR geometry.

4. UNIVERSE IMPORTATION AND MODEL PARAMETERS

The last major innovation of ELSA to manage complex models is the creation of EParameter objects. These objects have name and value attributes. The type of value can be str, int, bool, float, or an array. These objects are organized as an EParameters collection of objects on the same principle as Material and Materials objects in OpenMC. They are provided to a model and exported in the datasets that the OpenMC code takes as input. EParameter can also be easily imported from XML files.

ELSA also has functions to load base universes, materials, and parameters from a given XML file. As a result, it is possible to create specific sub-geometries in independent files and import them into a master model. A good example of this paradigm is the elaboration of the model of the TWIST experiment in TREAT (see Figure 7). Each assembly was designed as a standalone geometry. The shielding and the TWIST experiment were also developed as standalone geometries. All these geometries are then imported into a master geometry that creates the final model. All files load an options.xml file containing relevant EParameter objects, allowing the reactor configuration to be set dynamically (e.g., rod position, fuel temperature, water level in the TWIST capsule). Therefore, the user only needs to modify that file to generate the desired configuration of the core without having to modify each Python file. The workflow of the model generation is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Geometry of the TWIST experiment in TREAT.

Figure 8. Workflow to generate dynamic configurations.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the ELSA code, which has tools to help users create complex OpenMC models. First, the implementation of node-based geometry in ELSA was presented. Second, the multiple and parametric region generation capabilities were described. Third, the creation and importation of standalone geometries in ELSA alongside parameter objects that allow the user to create models representing specific configurations without having to modify the Python scripts. All these innovations allowed the rapid creation of workflows to study various experiments, such as the TWIST experiment in TREAT.

In the near future, the first version of ELSA will be released to the public under a open-source license. OpenMC may also benefit from the direct implementation of some capabilities available in ELSA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used INL AI Virtual Assistant (AiVA) in order to improve writing. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

This work was supported by INL Laboratory Directed Research & Development (LDRD) Program and is now supported through the DOE NE Fuel Cycle Research and Development Advanced Fuels Campaign Program under DOE Idaho Operations Office Contract DE-AC07-05ID14517.

This manuscript has been authored by Battelle Energy Alliance, LLC under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517 with the U.S. Department of Energy. The United States Government retains, and the publisher, by accepting the article for publication, acknowledges that the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, world-wide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this manuscript, or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes.

This research made use of the resources of the High Performance Computing Center at Idaho National Laboratory, which is supported by the Office of Nuclear Energy of the U.S. Department of Energy and the Nuclear Science User Facilities under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. L. Pope, C. B. Jensen, D. M. Gerstner, and J. R. Parry. "Transient Reactor Test (TREAT) Facility Design and Experiment Capability." *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 205**(10), pp. 1378–1386 (2019). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2019.1599615>.
- [2] C. P. Folsom, R. J. Armstrong, N. E. Woolstenhulme, D. D. Imholte, K. S. Anderson, and C. B. Jensen. "Thermal-hydraulic and Fuel Performance Scoping Studies of a Flowing Water Capsule in TREAT." In A. N. Society, editor, *TopFuel 2022* (2022). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1995776>.
- [3] T. Jing, S. Schunert, V. M. Labouré, M. D. DeHart, C.-S. Lin, and J. Ortensi. "Multiphysics Simulation of the NASA SIRIUS-CAL Fuel Experiment in the Transient Test Reactor Using Griffin." *Energies*, **volume 15**(17) (2022). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/15/17/6181>.
- [4] N. E. Woolstenhulme. "Status Report on Development of MARCH Module Designs." Technical Report 1572402, Idaho National Lab. (2019). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1572402>.
- [5] A. L. Balsmeier and T. P. Burnett. "NRIC EBR-II Test Bed Pre-Conceptual Design Report." Technical report, Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States) (2020). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1690269>.
- [6] N. Woolstenhulme, M. Cole, N. Martin, T. Reiss, J. Johnson, M. Lund, R. Claghorn, K. Gagnon, M. DeHart, W. Wieselquist, T. Cutler, C. Percher, A. Barto, and D. Algama. "SPARC - Plans for a

New Critical Experiment Facility with a Horizontal Split Table.” Technical Report INL/RPT-25-84855, Idaho National Laboratory (2025).

- [7] T. Goorley, M. James, T. Booth, F. Brown, J. Bull, L. J. Cox, J. Durkee, J. Elson, M. Fensin, R. A. Forster, J. Hendricks, H. G. Hughes, R. Johns, B. Kiedrowski, R. Martz, S. Mashnik, G. McKinney, D. Pelowitz, R. Prael, J. Sweezy, L. Waters, T. Wilcox, and T. Zukaitis. “Initial MCNP6 Release Overview.” *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 180**(3), pp. 298–315 (2012). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT11-135>.
- [8] S. M. Bowman. “SCALE 6: Comprehensive Nuclear Safety Analysis Code System.” *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 174**(2), pp. 126–148 (2011). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT10-163>.
- [9] J. Leppänen, M. Pusa, T. Viitanen, V. Valtavirta, and T. Kaltiaisenaho. “The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454914004095>. Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications and Monte Carlo 2013, SNA + MC 2013. Pluri- and Trans-disciplinarity, Towards New Modeling and Numerical Simulation Paradigms.
- [10] TRIPOLI-4® Project Team, Brun, E., Damian, F., Diop, C.M., Dumonteil, E., Hugot, F.X., Jouanne, C., Lee, Y.K., Malvagi, F., Mazzolo, A., Petit, O., Trama, J.C., Visonneau, T., and Zoia, A. “TRIPOLI-4®, CEA, EDF and AREVA Reference Monte Carlo Code.” In Array, editor, *SNA + MC 2013 - Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications + Monte Carlo*, p. 06023 (2014). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/snmc/201406023>.
- [11] P. K. Romano, N. E. Horelik, B. R. Herman, A. G. Nelson, B. Forget, and K. Smith. “OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for research and development.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 90–97 (2015). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030645491400379X>. Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications and Monte Carlo 2013, SNA + MC 2013. Pluri- and Trans-disciplinarity, Towards New Modeling and Numerical Simulation Paradigms.
- [12] P. A. Ferney, A. S. Chipman, T. V. Holschuh II, and C. B. Jensen. “Preliminary analysis of TREAT free-field experiments using openmc.” In *Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications + Monte Carlo* (2024). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/2369622>.
- [13] P. A. Ferney and N. P. Martin. “Implementation of Triply Periodic Minimal Surfaces (TPMS) as surface objects in OpenMC.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, p. 111661 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454925004785>.
- [14] P. Shriwise, X. Zhang, and A. Davis. “DAG-OpenMC: CAD-based geometry in OpenMC.” In *Proc. Amer. Nucl. Soc. Winter Meeting*, volume 122, pp. 395–398 (2020).
- [15] I. Antcheva, M. Ballintijn, B. Bellenot, M. Biskup, R. Brun, N. Buncic, P. Canal, D. Casadei, O. Couet, V. Fine, L. Franco, G. Ganis, A. Gheata, D. G. Maline, M. Goto, J. Iwaszkiewicz, A. Kreshuk, D. M. Segura, R. Maunder, L. Moneta, A. Naumann, E. Offermann, V. Onuchin, S. Panacek, F. Rademakers, P. Russo, and M. Tadel. “ROOT — A C++ framework for petabyte data storage, statistical analysis and visualization.” *Computer Physics Communications*, **volume 182**(6), pp. 1384–1385 (2011). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010465511000701>.
- [16] S. Agostinelli et al. “Geant4—a simulation toolkit.” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, **volume 506**(3), pp. 250–303 (2003). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900203013688>.